

Dyes Derived from Isatin. Azines and Indigoid Yat Dyes.

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In view of the interesting tinctorial properties of acenaphtheno-acenaphthazine and its various substituted products (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 679), the present investigation was undertaken to prepare similar azines in the isatin series and to study how far they are comparable with those of the corresponding compounds in the acenaphthenequinone series.

The paper deals with the preparation and properties of azine dyes obtained by condensing 2:3-diaminoacenaphthene (Sachs and Mosebach, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 2852) with isatin, 5-nitro-, and its 5:7-dinitro derivatives. These azines are yellow, brownish yellow and brown. The yellow shade developed on wool from acenaphthenoindazine is in no way inferior to that of the same shade obtained from acenaphtheno-acenaphthazine (*cf.* Guha, *loc. cit.*). It has also been observed that unlike acenaphthenoacenaphthazine, acenaphthenoindazine is not attended with a marked increase in the depth of the colour on introduction of nitro-groups. For the sake of convenience, a comparison of the colour of the dyeings on wool of some of these classes of compounds is given below:

Compound.	Colour of the dyeings on wool.
Acenaphthenoindazine	Yellow
Acenaphthenoacenaphthazine	Yellow
Acenaphtheno-5:7-dinitroindazine	Orange-yellow
Acenaphtheno-3:4-dinitroacenaphthazine	Chocolate

A few 2:3-naphthathiophene-indole-indigos are already known (Schwz. P. P., 105656/1924, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1926, **1B**, 497, 1890; Dutt, *Ber.*, 1934, **67**, 1325). Three more have now been obtained from 5-iodo-, 5-bromo-7-nitro-, and 5:7-dinitroisatin by condensation with 2:3-naphthoxythiophene (Friedländer and Woreschow, *Annalen*, 1912, **388**, 18). They resemble the indole-methylthionaphthene-indigos (*cf.* Guha and Basu-Mallick, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 396) in

giving rise to the soluble vats with an alkaline hydrosulphite and in uniformly developing on cotton fast shades. The violet, deep violet and blue-violet shades developed on cotton are deeper than those of the same shades obtained from chloro-, bromo-, and nitroisatin which were privately obtained for comparison from Dr. P. C. Dutta.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The azines described below were boiled with alcohol, in which they are sparingly soluble and finally crystallised.

Acenaphthenoindazine.

A solution of isatin (0.147 g.), 2,3-diaminoacenaphthene (0.184 g.), in boiling glacial acetic acid (15 c. c.) was boiled for 1 hour, when the colour of the solution turned reddish brown and the product separated in silky brownish yellow crystals. It was collected, washed and purified by a process similar to acenaphthenoacenaphthazine (Guha, *loc. cit.*). It melts above 310°. It is soluble in pyridine, moderately soluble in acetic acid and sparingly soluble in alcohol, benzene and xylene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a violet-blue colour and dyes wool in yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: N, 14.43. C₂₀H₁₃N₃ requires N, 14.23 per cent).

Acenaphtheno-5-nitroindazine.—5-Nitroisatin (0.288 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (35 c. c.), was mixed with a solution of 2,3-diaminoacenaphthene (0.276 g.) in acetic acid (15 c. c.). Crystalline precipitate separated from the resulting solution, which at first assumed a greenish-yellow colour quickly changing to brownish-red, the solution was boiled for half an hour and filtered hot, the precipitate washed with acetic acid and hot water. The product was crystallised from pyridine in small rectangles, subliming above 310°. It is soluble in nitrobenzene, and

pyridine; sparingly soluble in acetic acid, alcohol and acetone. It gives a deep blue colouration with strong sulphuric acid and dyes wool deep yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: N, 16.78. $C_{20}H_{12}O_2N_4$ requires N, 16.47 per cent).

Acenaphtheno-5:7-dinitroindazine was prepared in a similar way to the preceding compound from 5:7-dinitroisatin (0.237 g.) and the diaminoacenaphthene (0.184 g.) in glacial acetic acid (60 c. c.). The brown crystalline precipitate separated from xylene in microscopic needles subliming above 310° . It is moderately soluble in acetic acid and xylene, sparingly soluble in benzene, ethyl alcohol and amyl alcohol. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a deep blue colouration and dyes wool orange-yellow shades from an acid bath. (Found: N, 18.52. $C_{20}H_{11}O_4N_5$ requires N, 18.18 per cent).

The method of procedure adopted for the preparation of the indigoid dyes described below was the same in every case.

The isatin derivative and the 2:3-naphthoxythiophene were dissolved separately in boiling glacial acetic acid and the mixed solution was treated with a few c.c. of strong hydrochloric acid and shaken, the dye was precipitated at once. The mixture was heated to boiling for 10-14 minutes, filtered hot, the precipitate washed with acetic acid and hot water and purified by boiling successively with alcohol and acetic acid and crystallised.

These indigoid dyes are soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene and aniline; sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone, amyl alcohol, chloroform and benzene. They melt above 395° and on further heating volatilise evolving coloured vapours. The first two of the undermentioned dyes give a green colouration with strong sulphuric acid from which water reprecipitates the original dyes and they form deep yellow vat from which the dye is developed on cotton by atmospheric oxidation.

2:3-Naphthathiophene-3'-(5'-iodo)-indole-indigo.

It was prepared from 5-iodoisatin (1.365 g.) and 2:3-naphthoxythiophene (1 g.) in 120 c. c. of glacial acetic acid and 7 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. It separated from pyridine in fibre-like red-violet needles. It is moderately soluble in acetic acid and xylene. It dyes violet shades on cotton. (Found: S, 7.42. $C_{20}H_{10}O_2NIS$ requires S, 7.03 per cent).

2:3-Naphthathiophene-3'-(5'-bromo-7'-nitro)-indole-indigo separated as deep violet crystals by reacting 5-bromo-7-nitroisatin (0.542 g.) and the naphthoxythiophene (0.4 g.) in 70 c. c. of acetic acid and 4 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from pyridine as fine long needles. The dye is sparingly soluble in acetic acid, difficultly soluble in xylene. It dyes deep violet shades on cotton. (Found: Br, 17.59. $C_{20}H_9O_4N_2BrS$ requires Br, 17.66 per cent).

2:3-Naphthathiophene-3'-(5':7'-dinitro)-indole-indigo was obtained as dark violet crystals by the condensation of dinitroisatin (1.18 g.) and 2:3-naphthoxythiophene (1 g.) in 122 c. c. of acetic acid and 7.9 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from nitrobenzene in shining rectangular crystals. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a bluish green colouration and dyes cotton in blue-violet shades from an orange-yellow vat. (Found: S, 7.39. $C_{20}H_9O_6N_3S$ requires S, 7.63 per cent).